

A Systematic Literature Review of the Impacts on Health and Wellbeing through Indoor Greening: Search Strategy

Authors: Alejandro Jiménez Rios, Sukumar Natarajan, Louise King, Emma Taylor, Zina Abdulla, Richard Ball, Anna Chatzimichali, David Coley, Veronica Ferrandiz-Mas, Robert Grover, Sophia Hatzisavvidou, Tristan Kershaw, Murat Mustafa, Brian Rutter, Esha Trivedi, Caroline Watkinson

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1 Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review Literature Search (PRISMA-S)

1.1 Introduction

The quality of a systematic literature review heavily relies on the search strategy implemented for the information retrieval process. Nevertheless, search strategies are commonly not adequately reported. This document presents the search strategy adopted with the aim of exploring what the effects of indoor greening on occupant health and wellbeing are. It follows the PRISMA-S [1] checklist.

1.2 Search strategy

The recommended items to address in a search strategy according to the PRISMA-S checklist are presented in Table 1, Table 2, Table 3 and Table 4. This search strategy has been developed and documented to ensure transparency of the systematic review and facilitate its reproducibility.

Table 1. Information sources and methods.

Database name:	We will search the following bibliographic databases, selected for their comprehensive coverage of research in built environment studies, environmental psychology, public health, and indoor environmental quality: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scopus (Elsevier). • Web of Science (Clarivate). • PubMed (NIH)
Multi-database searching:	No multi-database platforms will be used; each database will be searched individually.
Study registries:	None. This review focuses on published literature, not clinical or project trial registries.
Online resources and browsing:	Searches will be conducted using the native interfaces of each database (Scopus), to ensure full functionality of advanced search features, filters, and controlled vocabularies where available.
Citation searching:	Backward citation searching will be conducted on the records included after the screening process, and only those references with titles that may seem relevant will be searched for retrieval and assessed for eligibility. Forward citation searching will not be conducted.
Contacts:	No further details will be searched by directly contacting authors, experts, manufacturers, or others.
Other methods:	No other methods will be used to explore grey literature to ensure reproducibility of the work.

Table 2. Search strategies.

Full search strategy:	The search queries (SQs) run were: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Scopus: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. ALL(("indoor greening" OR "indoor green infrastructure" OR "indoor vegetation" OR "green wall" OR "living wall" OR "vertical greenery system" OR "potted plants" OR "desktop plants" OR "indoor trees" OR "moss wall" OR "biofilter wall" OR "hydroponic system" OR "aquaponic system" OR "interior landscaping" OR "biophilic design") AND ("regenerative design" OR "net-positive health" OR "nature-based solution" OR "resilient building design" OR "health-centered architecture" OR "biophilic regeneration" OR "ecosystem services" OR "green retrofit") AND (buildin* OR hous* OR office*) AND NOT (urban OR outdoor OR landscape OR planning OR food OR animal*) AND PUBYEAR > 1999 AND PUBYEAR < 2027 AND PUBYEAR > 1999 AND PUBYEAR < 2027 AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"ar") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"ch") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"cp") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"re")) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"ENVI") OR LIMIT-TO (
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- SUBJAREA,"SOCI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"ENGI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"MEDI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"PSYC") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"NEUR") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"HEAL") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"ARTS")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE,"English"))
- ii. ALL(("indoor greening" OR "indoor green infrastructure" OR "indoor vegetation" OR "green wall" OR "living wall" OR "vertical greenery system" OR "potted plants" OR "desktop plants" OR "indoor trees" OR "moss wall" OR "biofilter wall" OR "hydroponic system" OR "aquaponic system" OR "interior landscaping" OR "biophilic design") AND ("climate change" OR "changing climate" OR "heat stress" OR "passive cooling" OR "thermal resilience" OR "climate adaptation" OR "indoor climate" OR "future scenarios" OR "temperature rise" OR "humidity variation") AND (build* OR hous* OR office*) AND NOT (urban OR outdoor OR landscape OR planning OR food OR animal*)) AND PUBYEAR > 1999 AND PUBYEAR < 2027 AND PUBYEAR > 1999 AND PUBYEAR < 2027 AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"ENVI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"ENGI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"SOCI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"MEDI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"PSYC") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"ARTS") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"HEAL"))) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"ar") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"ch") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"cp") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"re")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE,"English"))
- iii. ALL ((("human physical health" OR "human respiratory health" OR "lung function" OR "cardiovascular health" OR "immune response" OR "allergen exposure" OR "microbial exposure" OR "airborne pathogens" OR "bioaerosols" OR "indoor air quality" OR "IAQ" OR "CO₂ exposure" OR "VOC exposure" OR "PM2.5" OR "PM10") OR ("human mental health" OR "stress reduction" OR "anxiety" OR "depression" OR "cognitive function" OR "attention restoration" OR "psychological wellbeing" OR "human emotional health" OR "mood enhancement" OR "biophilic response" OR "nature therapy" OR "green therapy") OR ("occupant wellbeing" OR "holistic wellbeing" OR "quality of life" OR "perceived comfort" OR "satisfaction" OR "restorative environment" OR "indoor comfort" OR "human-centric design" OR "wellbeing indicators") OR ("microbial risks" OR "humidity imbalance" OR "mold exposure" OR "maintenance burden" OR "plant failure" OR "allergen sensitivity" OR "indoor pollution" OR "negative health effects")) AND ("indoor greening" OR "indoor green infrastructure" OR "indoor vegetation" OR "green wall" OR "living wall" OR "vertical greenery system" OR "potted plants" OR "desktop plants" OR "indoor trees" OR "moss wall" OR "biofilter wall" OR "hydroponic system" OR "aquaponic system" OR "interior landscaping" OR "biophilic design") AND NOT (urban OR outdoor OR landscape OR planning OR food* OR animal*)) AND PUBYEAR > 1999 AND PUBYEAR < 2027 AND PUBYEAR > 1999 AND PUBYEAR < 2027 AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"ENVI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"ENGI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"MEDI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"SOCI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"PSYC") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"ARTS") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"HEAL")) OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"NEUR"))) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"ar") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"cp") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"ch") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"re")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE,"English"))

2. Web of Science:

- i. TS=(("indoor greening" OR "indoor green infrastructure" OR "indoor vegetation" OR "green wall" OR "living wall" OR "vertical greenery system" OR "potted plants" OR "desktop plants" OR "indoor trees" OR "moss wall" OR "biofilter wall" OR "hydroponic system" OR "aquaponic system" OR "interior landscaping" OR "biophilic design") AND ("regenerative design" OR "net-positive health" OR "nature-based solution" OR "resilient building design"

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- OR "health-centered architecture" OR "biophilic regeneration" OR "ecosystem services" OR "green retrofit") AND (buildin* OR hous* OR office*) NOT (urban OR outdoor OR landscape OR planning OR food OR animal*)
 - ii. TS=((("indoor greening" OR "indoor green infrastructure" OR "indoor vegetation" OR "green wall" OR "living wall" OR "vertical greenery system" OR "potted plants" OR "desktop plants" OR "indoor trees" OR "moss wall" OR "biofilter wall" OR "hydroponic system" OR "aquaponic system" OR "interior landscaping" OR "biophilic design") AND ("climate change" OR "changing climate" OR "heat stress" OR "passive cooling" OR "thermal resilience" OR "climate adaptation" OR "indoor climate" OR "future scenarios" OR "temperature rise" OR "humidity variation") AND (build* OR hous* OR office*) NOT (urban OR outdoor OR landscape OR planning OR food OR animal*))
 - iii. TS=(((("human physical health" OR "human respiratory health" OR "lung function" OR "cardiovascular health" OR "immune response" OR "allergen exposure" OR "microbial exposure" OR "airborne pathogens" OR "bioaerosols" OR "indoor air quality" OR IAQ OR "CO₂ exposure" OR "VOC exposure" OR PM2.5 OR PM10) OR ("human mental health" OR "stress reduction" OR anxiety OR depression OR "cognitive function" OR "attention restoration" OR "psychological wellbeing" OR "human emotional health" OR "mood enhancement" OR "biophilic response" OR "nature therapy" OR "green therapy") OR ("occupant wellbeing" OR "holistic wellbeing" OR "quality of life" OR "perceived comfort" OR satisfaction OR "restorative environment" OR "indoor comfort" OR "human-centric design" OR "wellbeing indicators") OR ("microbial risks" OR "humidity imbalance" OR "mold exposure" OR "maintenance burden" OR "plant failure" OR "allergen sensitivity" OR "indoor pollution" OR "negative health effects")) AND ("indoor greening" OR "indoor green infrastructure" OR "indoor vegetation" OR "green wall" OR "living wall" OR "vertical greenery system" OR "potted plants" OR "desktop plants" OR "indoor trees" OR "moss wall" OR "biofilter wall" OR "hydroponic system" OR "aquaponic system" OR "interior landscaping" OR "biophilic design") NOT (urban OR outdoor OR landscape OR planning OR food* OR animal*))

3. PubMed:

- i. ("indoor greening"[tiab] OR "indoor green infrastructure"[tiab] OR "indoor vegetation"[tiab] OR "green wall"[tiab] OR "living wall"[tiab] OR "vertical greenery system"[tiab] OR "potted plants"[tiab] OR "desktop plants"[tiab] OR "indoor trees"[tiab] OR "moss wall"[tiab] OR "biofilter wall"[tiab] OR "hydroponic system"[tiab] OR "aquaponic system"[tiab] OR "interior landscaping"[tiab] OR "biophilic design"[tiab]) AND ("regenerative design"[tiab] OR "net-positive health"[tiab] OR "nature-based solution"[tiab] OR "resilient building design"[tiab] OR "health-centered architecture"[tiab] OR "biophilic regeneration"[tiab] OR "ecosystem services"[tiab] OR "green retrofit"[tiab]) AND (building[tiab] OR buildings[tiab] OR housing[tiab] OR house[tiab] OR houses[tiab] OR office[tiab] OR offices[tiab]) NOT (urban[tiab] OR outdoor[tiab] OR landscape[tiab] OR planning[tiab] OR food[tiab] OR animal[tiab] OR animals[tiab]) AND ("2000"[dp] : "2026"[dp]) AND english[la] AND (Journal Article[pt] OR Review[pt])
 - ii. ("indoor greening"[tiab] OR "indoor green infrastructure"[tiab] OR "indoor vegetation"[tiab] OR "green wall"[tiab] OR "living wall"[tiab] OR "vertical greenery system"[tiab] OR "potted plants"[tiab] OR "desktop plants"[tiab] OR "indoor trees"[tiab] OR "moss wall"[tiab] OR "biofilter wall"[tiab] OR "hydroponic system"[tiab] OR "aquaponic system"[tiab] OR "interior landscaping"[tiab] OR "biophilic design"[tiab]) AND ("climate change"[tiab] OR "changing climate"[tiab] OR "heat stress"[tiab] OR "passive cooling"[tiab] OR "thermal resilience"[tiab] OR "climate adaptation"[tiab] OR "indoor climate"[tiab] OR "future scenarios"[tiab] OR "temperature rise"[tiab] OR "humidity variation"[tiab]) AND (building[tiab] OR buildings[tiab] OR housing[tiab] OR house[tiab] OR houses[tiab] OR office[tiab] OR offices[tiab]) NOT (urban[tiab] OR outdoor[tiab]
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	<p>OR landscape[tiab] OR planning[tiab] OR food[tiab] OR animal[tiab] OR animals[tiab]) AND ("2000"[dp] : "2026"[dp]) AND english[la] AND (Journal Article[pt] OR Review[pt])</p> <p>iii. (("human physical health"[tiab] OR "human respiratory health"[tiab] OR "lung function"[tiab] OR "cardiovascular health"[tiab] OR "immune response"[tiab] OR "allergen exposure"[tiab] OR "microbial exposure"[tiab] OR "airborne pathogens"[tiab] OR "bioaerosols"[tiab] OR "indoor air quality"[tiab] OR IAQ[tiab] OR "CO2 exposure"[tiab] OR "VOC exposure"[tiab] OR PM2.5[tiab] OR PM10[tiab]) OR ("human mental health"[tiab] OR "stress reduction"[tiab] OR anxiety[tiab] OR depression[tiab] OR "cognitive function"[tiab] OR "attention restoration"[tiab] OR "psychological wellbeing"[tiab] OR "human emotional health"[tiab] OR "mood enhancement"[tiab] OR "biophilic response"[tiab] OR "nature therapy"[tiab] OR "green therapy"[tiab]) OR ("occupant wellbeing"[tiab] OR "holistic wellbeing"[tiab] OR "quality of life"[tiab] OR "perceived comfort"[tiab] OR satisfaction[tiab] OR "restorative environment"[tiab] OR "indoor comfort"[tiab] OR "human-centric design"[tiab] OR "wellbeing indicators"[tiab]) OR ("microbial risks"[tiab] OR "humidity imbalance"[tiab] OR "mold exposure"[tiab] OR "maintenance burden"[tiab] OR "plant failure"[tiab] OR "allergen sensitivity"[tiab] OR "indoor pollution"[tiab] OR "negative health effects"[tiab])) AND ("indoor greening"[tiab] OR "indoor green infrastructure"[tiab] OR "indoor vegetation"[tiab] OR "green wall"[tiab] OR "living wall"[tiab] OR "vertical greenery system"[tiab] OR "potted plants"[tiab] OR "desktop plants"[tiab] OR "indoor trees"[tiab] OR "moss wall"[tiab] OR "biofilter wall"[tiab] OR "hydroponic system"[tiab] OR "aquaponic system"[tiab] OR "interior landscaping"[tiab] OR "biophilic design"[tiab]) NOT (urban[tiab] OR outdoor[tiab] OR landscape[tiab] OR planning[tiab] OR food[tiab] OR foods[tiab] OR animal[tiab] OR animals[tiab]) AND ("2000"[dp] : "2026"[dp]) AND english[la] AND (Journal Article[pt] OR Review[pt])</p>
Limits and restrictions:	The search was not limited by field, ALL search fields were considered in Scopus. Equivalent searches were conducted in Web of Science and PubMed.
Search filters:	<p>No externally developed or pre-defined search filters (e.g., systematic reviews filters, health outcomes filters) will be used. The search strategies will be developed specifically for this review and will not rely on published or validated filters. The following filters will be applied:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subject areas: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Environmental Science ○ Social Sciences ○ Engineering ○ Arts and Humanities ○ Medicine ○ Psychology ○ Neuroscience ○ Health Professions • Years: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 2000 to 2026 • Document type: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Article ○ Review ○ Book chapter ○ Conference paper • Language: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ English
Prior work:	The search strategies will be developed independently for this systematic review and will not be adapted from any prior published literature searches.
Updates:	No update method will be used as the final manuscript will be completed shortly after the search had been performed.
Dates of searchers:	The search was conducted on 03/02/2026.

Table 3. Peer review.

Peer review:	The search strategy document will be made available online along with the systematic review protocol in the OSF website under project code 8JPQ4 [2].
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Table 4. Managing records.

Total records:	<p>The total records found (743) will be reported in accordance to the PRISMA 2020 flow diagram for systematic reviews [3]. The number of records identified with each of the search queries reported were:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Scopus:<ol style="list-style-type: none">i. SQ1 = 28ii. SQ2 = 180iii. SQ3 = 3292. Web of Science:<ol style="list-style-type: none">i. SQ1 = 8ii. SQ2 = 22iii. SQ3 = 1623. PubMed:<ol style="list-style-type: none">i. SQ1 = 0ii. SQ2 = 0iii. SQ3 = 14 <p>A FAIR bibliographic database has been created with all the records identified at this stage [4].</p>
Deduplication:	The deduplication process was conducted manually with the help of Excel deduplication tools by filtering duplicate titles. After manually cross filtering duplicate records 87 duplicated values were found and removed. 656 records remained.

References

1. Rethlefsen, M.L., et al., *PRISMA-S: an extension to the PRISMA Statement for Reporting Literature Searches in Systematic Reviews*. *Systematic Reviews*, 2021. **10**(1): p. 39. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-020-01542-z>.
2. Jiménez Rios, A., et al., *Impacts on Health and Wellbeing Through Indoor Greening: OSF Project*. 2025. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/8JPQ4>.
3. Page, M.J., et al., *The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews*. *BMJ*, 2021. **372**: p. n71. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n71>.
4. Jiménez Rios, A., et al., *Bibliographic Dataset for the Systematic Literature Review of the Impacts on Health and Wellbeing through Indoor Greening*. 2025. Zenodo. Available from. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17928248>.

Annex A

Table 5. History of changes.

Version	Publication date	Change
1.0	14/12/2025	Initial version.
2.0	03/02/2026	Web of Science and PubMed were added, "Reviews" were also included, and backwards citation search adopted. New search was conducted on 03/02/2026.

